
Psychosocial Dimensions of Prenatal Maternal Well-Being: A Review of Literature

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20100063>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 22-04-2026

Published: 10-05-2026

Keywords:

Prenatal mothers, stress, social support, marital satisfaction, COVID-19, maternal mental health

ABSTRACT

Pregnancy is an important phase in a woman's life that brings along not only physical changes but also emotional and social adjustments. While medical care during pregnancy mainly focuses on physical health, the psychological and social wellbeing of mothers often receives less attention. This paper attempts to bring together findings from existing studies on key psychosocial factors such as stress, fear of childbirth, social support, marital satisfaction, and disruptions caused by COVID-19 pandemic among prenatal mothers. The review is based on secondary sources including research articles, books, and reports. Most studies suggest that a considerable number of women experience psychological distress during pregnancy, which may affect both maternal and foetal outcomes. Fear of childbirth emerges as a critical psychosocial factor influencing birthing preferences and postpartum mental health. At the same time, support from family especially spouses play a major role in helping women cope with challenges and improving pregnancy outcomes. Marital satisfaction emerges as a significant predictor of maternal mental health, while pandemic related conditions have altered prenatal care experiences. Findings indicate that psychosocial factors are deeply interconnected and play a crucial role in shaping prenatal experiences and outcomes. The review underscores the need for a holistic social work driven approach that incorporate psychosocial interventions into prenatal care. This paper contributes to social work

education and practice by advocating for strengthened psychosocial frameworks in maternal healthcare.

Introduction

Pregnancy is often described as a period of joy and anticipation. However, it is equally a time of significant psychological adjustment. Beyond the visible physiological changes, women undergo emotional, cognitive, and relational shifts that shape their overall well-being. In recent years, there has been increasing recognition that maternal mental health during pregnancy is not only important for the mother but also has lasting implications for fetal development and child outcomes (Kinsella et al., 2009).

Traditional maternal healthcare has largely focused on physical health indicators such as nutrition, foetal growth, and medical complications. Emerging research suggests that psychosocial dimensions such as stress, fear, quality of relationships, and social support play a crucial role in shaping pregnancy experiences (Hobel et al., 2008). These factors influence not only how women cope with pregnancy but also how they engage with healthcare systems and prepare for childbirth. Understanding these psychosocial determinants is particularly important in the context of social work practice, where professionals engage directly with pregnant women and their families.

This review attempts to bring together key psychosocial dimensions influencing prenatal maternal well-being, with a focus on stress during pregnancy, fear of childbirth, social support, marital satisfaction, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. By examining these factors collectively, the paper aims to present a more holistic understanding of maternal well-being and to identify gaps for future research and practice.

Methodology

This paper adopts a narrative review approach to synthesize existing literature on psychosocial aspects of prenatal maternal well-being. Relevant studies were identified through academic sources including peer-reviewed journal articles, books, and reports related to maternal mental health.

The selection of literature was guided by five key themes such as stress during pregnancy, fear of childbirth, social support, marital satisfaction, and the impact of COVID-19. The selection of articles from various academic databases including empirical studies that provided clear methodologies and significant findings, along with foundational theoretical works that contributed to understanding the psychosocial dimensions or factors were selected.

The review focuses on categorizing important findings into five core thematic domains such as stress and anxiety, fear of childbirth, the role of social support, marital satisfaction, and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic to develop a coherent understanding of psychosocial influences on pregnancy.

Prenatal Stress and Maternal Mental Health

Stress during pregnancy has been widely discussed as a major factor affecting maternal and foetal outcomes. Research indicates that women who experience higher levels of emotional stress during pregnancy are more likely to report anxiety-related difficulties in the postpartum period (Zietlow et al., 2019). At the same time, stress has also been associated with adverse birth outcomes such as low birth weight and preterm delivery (Loomans et al., 2013).

Large-scale research studies have shown that a significant proportion of pregnant women experience some form of psychosocial stress. These stressors may arise from financial concerns, health-related anxieties, or changes in personal relationships. These interactions of several factors together influence the neurological development of the child in later years resulting in neurodevelopmental disorders (Andrews, 2012).

Biological explanations suggest that mechanisms such as dysregulation of the Hypothalamic Pituitary Adrenal (HPA) axis and intrauterine transmission of cortisol have been identified as pathways through which maternal stress affects hormonal functioning and thereby influencing the foetus' neurological development (Kinsella et al., 2009).

At the same time, it is important to note that stress does not operate in a simple cause and effect manner. It interacts with other psychological and social factors, making its impact complex and varied across individuals. There remains a need for culturally contextualized studies and longitudinal research exploring long-term developmental outcomes.

Fear of Childbirth

Fear of childbirth is another important psychological dimension that shapes pregnancy experiences. For many women, childbirth is associated with uncertainty, pain, and concerns about safety. These fears may stem from personal experiences, stories shared by others, lack of adequate information or perceived lack of support from healthcare providers.

Studies have identified ten key elements of fear of childbirth, including fear of pain, fear of harm to the baby, fear of medical interventions, fear of the unpredictable, fear of coping with labor and fear of losing

control during labour (Slade et al., 2019). In some cases, these fears are strong enough to influence women's preferences regarding the mode of delivery, with some opting for C-section (cesarean sections) to avoid anticipated distress (Sluijs et al., 2020).

Qualitative research has shown that fear of childbirth is often deeply emotional and shaped by traumatic birth narratives shared by others (Wigert et al., 2020). Women frequently report feeling unheard or excluded from decision-making processes during childbirth. This highlights the importance of addressing emotional concerns during pregnancy rather than focusing solely on physical preparation.

Despite the development of measurement tools, variations in assessment methods result in differing prevalence rates of fear of childbirth across studies over seven countries (Nilsson et al., 2018). This indicates the need for standardized tools and culturally sensitive interventions to address fear of childbirth effectively.

Social Support and Pregnancy Outcomes

Social support plays a critical role in stress buffering and promoting positive pregnancy outcomes. Support can come from multiple sources, including partners, family members, friends, and other healthcare professionals. Emotional support helps women cope with stress and anxiety, while practical support assists them in managing daily challenges. Evidence suggests that women with higher levels of social support experience fewer depressive symptoms and reduced pregnancy complications (Elsenbruch et al., 2007).

Pregnant women had to overcome obstacles like financial issues, transportation problems, psychological concerns and work-related issues. Studies suggested that the support from the partner aided the foundation for strong and positive prenatal care (Pierce et al., 1996). The role of the partner was reported especially significant, as they are often the primary source of emotional reassurance. Women who receive consistent support from their partners demonstrate better mental health outcomes compared to those with limited support. However, extended family systems also contribute significantly to coping mechanisms during pregnancy (Hobfall, 1986).

Disparities exist in access to support, particularly among vulnerable populations such as adolescent mothers. While some studies report higher levels of support among younger mothers, the absence of stable partner relationships may increase their vulnerability to postpartum depression.

Marital Satisfaction and Prenatal Health

Marital satisfaction is the concept closely related to social support and is closely linked to maternal mental health and overall pregnancy outcomes. The quality of the relationship between partners has a direct impact on a woman's emotional experience during pregnancy.

Research indicates that women in supportive and satisfying relationships experience lower levels of anxiety and emotional distress during pregnancy. They are more likely to feel supported, communicate openly, cope effectively with challenges and tend to have increased sense of security. Women who report higher marital satisfaction are most likely to have better psychological outcomes during pregnancy (Røsland et al., 2011).

Conversely, marital conflict and dissatisfaction are associated with increased psychological distress and adverse pregnancy outcomes. Strained relationships may reduce emotional resilience and negatively affect maternal well-being and in some cases pregnancy loss. Studies also suggest that marital satisfaction can predict levels of anxiety during pregnancy, highlighting its importance as a psychosocial determinant transitioning from couples to parents (Lawrence et al., 2008).

Marital satisfaction also influences how couples prepare for parenthood, making it an important factor in both prenatal and postnatal adjustment. Interventions such as couple counselling and sexual health education have shown positive effects in improving marital satisfaction (Masoumi et al, 2017). These findings underscore the need to include relational dynamics in prenatal care and psychosocial interventions.

Impact of COVID-19 on Prenatal Care

The COVID-19 pandemic introduced a new layer of uncertainty and stress for pregnant women. Fear of infection, restrictions on in-person visits to the hospitals, and changes in healthcare delivery created additional challenges during pregnancy (Javaid et al., 2021).

Many women reported increased anxiety due to concerns about their own health and the health of their unborn child. Social distancing measures also reduced access to traditional support systems, leading to feelings of isolation (Wu et al., 2020). Others perceived a decline in the quality of care. Studies also highlight increased levels of anxiety and depression associated with fears of virus transmission to the fetus (Kotlar et al., 2021).

While tele-health emerged as an alternative, it was not equally accessible to all. Disruptions in healthcare services made it difficult for some women to access regular antenatal care. Although digital healthcare solutions provided alternatives, challenges such as accessibility, reliability of information, technological and financial barriers were reported to largely affect pregnant mothers in rural communities (Bankar & Gosh, 2022). The pandemic highlighted the importance of adaptable healthcare systems that can address both physical and psychological needs during crises.

Discussion

The findings from the reviewed literature suggest that prenatal maternal well-being cannot be understood through a single lens. Instead, it is shaped by the interaction of multiple factors, including psychological experiences, relationship dynamics, and external circumstances. Stress, fear, social support, and marital satisfaction are interconnected and collectively influence maternal well-being and birth outcomes.

Stress and fear of childbirth emerge as closely linked experiences, often reinforcing each other. Factors like Gravida, Educational status and monthly family income has direct influence on the stress experienced by women during pregnancy. When left unaddressed, they can negatively influence both maternal mental health and pregnancy outcomes.

The presence of strong support in three domains such as tangible, informational and emotional support can significantly reduce these negative effects by providing emotional reassurance and practical assistance.

Marital satisfaction further strengthens this support system, highlighting the importance of partner relationships in shaping maternal experiences. A supportive partner not only helps reduce stress but also contributes to a more positive outlook towards pregnancy and childbirth.

The COVID-19 pandemic adds an important dimension by demonstrating how external crises can intensify existing vulnerabilities. It underscores the need for healthcare systems to address psychological well-being alongside physical health.

Overall, the literature points towards the need for a more integrated approach to maternal care that recognizes the interconnected nature of these factors.

Research Gap

While there is considerable research on individual aspects of prenatal maternal well-being, several gaps remain. One major limitation is that many studies examine factors such as stress, fear of childbirth, and social support separately, without exploring how they interact with each other.

There is also a lack of context-specific research, particularly in developing countries where cultural norms and family structures differ significantly. This limits the applicability of existing findings to diverse populations.

Most studies focus on identifying problems rather than evaluating interventions. There is a need for more research on practical strategies that can improve maternal mental health during pregnancy. The long-term impact of pandemic-related stress on maternal and child outcomes are not sufficiently explored, indicating the need for further investigation.

Implications for Social Work Practice

The findings of this review have important implications for social work practice, particularly in the field of maternal and child health. Social workers play an important role in identifying and addressing psychosocial concerns during pregnancy.

Interventions should focus on:

- Incorporating routine psychological assessment into antenatal care. Social workers can help identify stress, anxiety, and fear of childbirth at an early stage and provide appropriate support.
- Strengthening existing support systems. Social workers can work with families to improve communication, enhance partner involvement, and build supportive environments for pregnant women.
- Ensuring access to healthcare. Providing accurate information about childbirth and coping strategies can help reduce fear and increase confidence among expectant mothers.
- Being prepared for situations like the COVID-19 pandemic. Social workers can play a key role in ensuring continuity of care, facilitating access to services, and addressing the emotional needs of women facing isolation and uncertainty.

Conclusion

Prenatal maternal health is a multidimensional concept which is influenced by various psychological factors such as stress and fear, social factors such as marital satisfaction and social support, and external influences such as the COVID-19 pandemic and all these factors collectively contribute to shaping pregnancy experiences. Addressing these factors is essential for improving maternal and child health outcomes.

This review highlights the need for a holistic approach to maternal care that integrates psychological and social dimensions alongside medical care. Addressing these factors is essential not only for improving maternal well-being but also for ensuring positive outcomes for future generations.

Social workers play a crucial role in bridging gaps between healthcare providers and families, advocating for maternal well-being, and delivering psychosocial interventions. Future research should focus on integrated, culturally relevant approaches and strengthen the role of social work in maternal healthcare systems.

References

- Andrews, S. (2012). *Stress solutions for pregnant moms: How breaking free from stress can boost your baby's potential*. Twin Span Press.
- Bankar, S., Ghosh, D. Accessing Antenatal Care (ANC) services during the COVID-19 first wave: insights into decision-making in rural India. *Reprod Health* 19, 158 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-022-01446-2>
- Elsenbruch, S., Benson, S., Rucke, M., Rose, M., Dudenhausen, J., Pincus-Knackstedt, M. K., Klapp, B. F., & Arck, P. C. (2007). Social support during pregnancy: effects on maternal depressive symptoms, smoking and pregnancy outcome. *Human reproduction (Oxford, England)*, 22(3), 869–877. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/del432>
- Hobel, C. J., Goldstein, A., & Barrett, E. S. (2008). Psychosocial stress and pregnancy outcome. *Clinical obstetrics and gynecology*, 51(2), 333–348. <https://doi.org/10.1097/GRF.0b013e31816f2709>
- Hobfoll, S. E. (Ed.). (1986). *Stress, social support, and women*. Hemisphere Publishing Corp.

- Javaid, S., Barringer, S., Compton, S. D., Kaselitz, E., Muzik, M., & Moyer, C. A. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on prenatal care in the United States: Qualitative analysis from a survey of 2519 pregnant women. *Midwifery*, 98, 102991. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.midw.2021.102991>
- Johnson, A. R., Kumar, M. G., Jacob, R., Jessie, M. A., Mary, F., Agrawal, T., & Raman, V. (2019). Fear of Childbirth among Pregnant Women Availing Antenatal Services in a Maternity Hospital in Rural Karnataka. *Indian journal of psychological medicine*, 41(4), 318–322. https://doi.org/10.4103/IJPSYM.IJPSYM_292_18
- Kim, T. H., Connolly, J. A., & Tamim, H. (2014). The effect of social support around pregnancy on postpartum depression among Canadian teen mothers and adult mothers in the maternity experiences survey. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*, 14, 162. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2393-14-162>
- Kinsella, M. T., & Monk, C. (2009). Impact of maternal stress, depression and anxiety on fetal neurobehavioral development. *Clinical obstetrics and gynecology*, 52(3), 425–440. <https://doi.org/10.1097/GRF.0b013e3181b52df1>
- Kotlar, B., Gerson, E. M., Petrillo, S., Langer, A., & Tiemeier, H. (2021). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on maternal and perinatal health: a scoping review. *Reproductive health*, 18(1), 10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-021-01070-6>
- Kumbeni, M. T., Apanga, P. A., Yeboah, E. O., & Lettor, I. B. K. (2021). Knowledge and preventive practices towards COVID-19 among pregnant women seeking antenatal services in Northern Ghana. *PloS one*, 16(6), e0253446. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253446>
- Lawrence, E., Rothman, A. D., Cobb, R. J., Rothman, M. T., & Bradbury, T. N. (2008). Marital satisfaction across the transition to parenthood. *Journal of family psychology : JFP : journal of the Division of Family Psychology of the American Psychological Association (Division 43)*, 22(1), 41–50. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0893-3200.22.1.41>
- Loomans, E. M., van Dijk, A. E., Vrijkotte, T. G., van Eijsden, M., Stronks, K., Gemke, R. J., & Van den Bergh, B. R. (2013). Psychosocial stress during pregnancy is related to adverse birth outcomes: results from a large multi-ethnic community-based birth cohort. *European journal of public health*, 23(3), 485–491. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/cks097>
- Masoumi, S. Z., Kazemi, F., Nejati, B., Parsa, P., & Karami, M. (2017). Effect of Sexual Counseling on Marital Satisfaction of Pregnant Women Referring to Health Centers in Malayer (Iran): An

educational randomized experimental study. *Electronic physician*, 9(1), 3598–3604. <https://doi.org/10.19082/3598>

- Nagabharana, T., Joseph, S.V., Prabhu, M.P. et al. Exploring sources of social support during pregnancy- a qualitative study in rural southern India. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 26, 411 (2026). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-026-08888-7>
- Nilsson, C., Hessman, E., Sjöblom, H., Dencker, A., Jangsten, E., Mollberg, M., Patel, H., Sparud-Lundin, C., Wigert, H., & Begley, C. (2018). Definitions, measurements and prevalence of fear of childbirth: a systematic review. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*, 18(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-018-1659-7>
- Pais, Maria & Pai, Murlidhar & Kamath, Asha & George, Anice & Noronha, Judith & Nayak, Baby & Nambiar, Jayaram & H., Ganapathi. (2014). Stress among Antenatal Women in India. *International Journal Of Nursing Care.. International Journal Of Nursing Care.* 2. 63-67. 10.5958/2320-8651.2014.01272.1.
- Pierce, Gregory & Sarason, Barbara & Sarason, Irwin. (1996). *Handbook of Social Support and the Family.* 10.1007/978-1-4899-1388-3.
- Røsand, G. M., Slinning, K., Eberhard-Gran, M., Røysamb, E., & Tambs, K. (2011). Partner relationship satisfaction and maternal emotional distress in early pregnancy. *BMC public health*, 11, 161. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-11-161>
- Salehi F, Shahhosseini Z. Association Between Women’s Marital Satisfaction and Anxiety During Pregnancy. *Iran J Psychiatry Behav Sci.* 2017;11(3):e7937. doi: <https://doi.org/10.17795/ijpbs-7937>
- Slade, P., Balling, K., Sheen, K., & Houghton, G. (2019). Establishing a valid construct of fear of childbirth: findings from in-depth interviews with women and midwives. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*, 19(1), 96. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-019-2241-7>
- Sluijs, A. M., Wijma, K., Cleiren, M. P. H. D., van Lith, J. M. M., & Wijma, B. (2020). Preferred and actual mode of delivery in relation to fear of childbirth. *Journal of psychosomatic obstetrics and gynaecology*, 41(4), 266–274. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0167482X.2019.1708319>

- Uwambaye, P., Nyiringango, G., Musabwasoni, S. M. G., Husain, A., Nessa, K., & Razzaque, M. S. (2020). COVID-19 Pandemic: Adaptation in Antenatal Care for Better Pregnancy Outcomes. *Frontiers in global women's health*, 1, 599327. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgwh.2020.599327>
- Wigert, H., Nilsson, C., Dencker, A., Begley, C., Jangsten, E., Sparud-Lundin, C., Mollberg, M., & Patel, H. (2020). Women's experiences of fear of childbirth: a metasynthesis of qualitative studies. *International journal of qualitative studies on health and well-being*, 15(1), 1704484. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17482631.2019.1704484>
- Wu, H., Sun, W., Huang, X., Yu, S., Wang, H., Bi, X., Sheng, J., Chen, S., Akinwunmi, B., Zhang, C. J. P., & Ming, W. K. (2020). Online Antenatal Care During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of medical Internet research*, 22(7), e19916. <https://doi.org/10.2196/19916>
- Zietlow, A. L., Nonnenmacher, N., Reck, C., Ditzen, B., & Müller, M. (2019). Emotional Stress During Pregnancy - Associations With Maternal Anxiety Disorders, Infant Cortisol Reactivity, and Mother-Child Interaction at Pre-school Age. *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 2179. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02179>